

Professors' identity and interaction in a culturally diverse higher education environment

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1. Introduction

Due to the increased migration and mobility in the last decades, and especially with the later Ukraine-Russia conflict, individuals have been moving across the world, often from lower-income to higher-income countries (Guichard et al., 2022; Porru & Baldo, 2022). These events have contributed to the propagation of religiously, culturally and linguistically diversified societies, intensifying the need for learning and teaching about intercultural communication, as means of diminishing prejudice and discrimination (Tualaulelei & Halse, 2021). In such an environment, it becomes essential to work on perceptions about interculturality, personal understanding, values and rights, while emphasizing the expression of respect and tolerance, which can be achieved through intercultural education (Pareja de Vicente et al., 2021). However, for educators to be able to impact learners in the classroom and instruct on intercultural competency, they must possess professional preparation and development related to interaction in culturally diversified settings (Tualaulelei & Halse, 2021).

The previous literature extensively observes students' perceptions of the higher education system as the measure of the educational quality and universities' success, lacking the identification of the institutions and their employees as an additional influencing factor (Binnawas et al., 2020). Additionally, intercultural training for enhancing professors' and students' competencies, intercultural educational sensitivity and the necessity of those for professors and students has been addressed in prior research (Auer & Tsiatsos, 2018). Nevertheless, no investigation deepens into the intercultural competencies' impact on professors' performance or antecedents as the tool of diversity-competent, aware and sensitive communities in the long run.

Drawing on the evidence that describes teaching practices, support and pedagogy as imperative in the evaluation of higher education, it is likely that professors with mature professional identities will be prone

to innovate in their education practices, deal with education novelties and grow professionally (Abu-Alruz & Khasawneh, 2013; Garwe, 2015). With this in mind, we propose to explore professors' intercultural competence expressed through cultural diversity enthusiasm, self-efficacy and commitment to social justice, as determined by professors' identity with their profession, especially their interaction with students, while, in turn, shaping further engagement with the job.

The following content of the study presents the theoretical background that serves as a fundament for the hypotheses proposition (section 2), the explanation of the methodology employed for the research (section 3), the results of the analysis (section 4) and the discussion of the findings and conclusions (section 5), commenting on the implications of the investigation and future research possibilities related to the study.

2. Theoretical background

2.1. Cultural diversity in higher education

The diversity present in many populations nowadays is often a result of the increasing globalization and migration, mobilizing people worldwide (Goodwin, 2020). In the Western Balkan, as well, multiple cultural and ethnic groups have comprised the society since many years ago. The multicultural societies of the Western Balkan countries are represented by interethnic and interreligious relationships, shaped not only by earlier historical events, but also by the recent refugee crisis, establishing a cultural diversity that defies many aspects of the society (Hadžić, 2020). These events have contributed to classrooms where students have become culturally, religiously and even linguistically different, emphasizing the need to capacitate instructors for intercultural professional development and ensure interculturally competent generations (Tualaulelei & Halse, 2021). It is the classroom where students can gain a more comprehensive understanding and knowledge of communication and contribution to a culturally diverse society (Petrović et al., 2016). However, for this preparation to be adequate and valuable, the necessary requirement is to count on professors equipped with the knowledge, strategies and tools essential for managing the singularity coming from cultural diversity (Zlatković et al., 2017).

It has been widely discussed in the literature on the importance of proper education for teachers on intercultural skills and competencies, and it has been clearly emphasized the necessity for professors' training and educational institutions' efforts towards this preparation (Müller et al., 2020; Tualaulelei & Halse, 2022). However, the actual outcomes of cultural diversity positive attitudes or the benefits to professors' performance and the relation with their aptitudes, have not been the focus of research. Understanding how professors' capacities interrelate with their enactment in a multicultural teaching environment might be the key to engaged employees, dedicated to educating the youth about the integrity of a culturally diverse society. Engagement, as the vital element for achieving organizational quality,

productivity and effectiveness, is an enduring state characterizing professors' identification, commitment and efficacy in the delivery of their work responsibilities with substantial dynamism, dedication and passion (Sharafizad & Redmond, 2020; Whitten, 2016). Therefore, bearing in mind the multicultural and multi-ethnic societies of the Western Balkan countries, in order to precisely observe the direction of professors' engagement, it is vital to observe the factors that determine this engagement, especially those describing professors' performance in a multicultural higher education setting (Pryshliak et al., 2020). As already mentioned in the previous literature, professors' capacity to act in a culturally diverse environment can be a substantial predictor of their performance (Müller et al., 2020). However, it might not be sufficient to observe only the professors' disposition to deal with culturally diverse environments, mainly because of the lack of formal training they receive from their institutions (Starčević et al., 2022). Hence, it is important to evaluate also their identification with their job, as the skills and tendency to perform their responsibilities, as well as their values and preferences that contribute to organizational success, as the precursor of attitudes specific to multicultural environments (Hayes & Corrie, 2020; Stricker et al., 2019).

2.2. Intercultural competence

In the Western Balkan countries, it is not unusual for professors to work in a multicultural environment, with colleagues and students from different cultural or ethnic backgrounds (Petrović et al., 2016). Intercultural competence has been widely defined in the literature as “the ability to communicate effectively and appropriately in intercultural situations based on one's intercultural knowledge, skills, and attitudes” (Deardorff, 2006, p. 247). Therefore, if professors' professional development is not in line with the skills and attitudes necessary for working in a culturally diversified environment, it can be a source of concern and unproductive work (Müller et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2015). Furthermore, professors' engagement in the education of students from different cultural backgrounds can be obstructed by their lack of competencies and motivation to work in such an environment, underlining the importance of observing the engagement as the goal to be reached towards the path to achieving valuable higher education system (Zlatković et al., 2017).

In order for professors to be capable of involving in stimulating positive cultural and social change, which is vital for the development of multicultural teaching environments, they need to possess awareness, values and practices to support the educational and social success of culturally different settings (Picower, 2015; Walton et al., 2013). The elements that have been considered to describe intercultural competencies encompass effort, perseverance, enthusiasm, and motivation to reach out to students and assist them in achieving satisfactory learning outcomes (Kunter, 2013; Kunter et al., 2011). Professors who show solidarity and empathy in the classroom dedicate to social justice and value the challenge of the diverse

environment, and perceive their work as a duty to empower students and teachers to act in a multicultural society (Samuels et al., 2019; Tualualelei & Halse, 2022). Accordingly, in this study, we focus on higher education professors' enthusiasm, self-efficacy and social justice commitment in performing in a culturally diverse environment, capacitating the professors to act toward social change promotion (Cochran-Smith et al., 2008). Those elements have been defined in the previous literature as fundamental for designating professors' cultural diversity capacities (Petrović et al., 2016). However, their relation and impact on the broader professors' enactment have not been systematically explored.

Namely, *cultural diversity enthusiasm* expresses professors' preparedness and pleasure to educate and interact in a multicultural classroom. It designates their perceptions of the working tasks as joyful and challenging, leading professors to involve with eagerness in a culturally diverse setting. *Cultural diversity self-efficacy* describes professors' competence and confidence to encourage students' positive learning outcomes and support their achievements. Self-efficient professors feel sure in their approach to creating learning conditions according to the needs of a multicultural classroom. Professors' *commitment to social justice* indicates their motivation and willingness to encourage equality and prevent conflict in a multicultural classroom. Their reaction to discrimination or exclusion serves as encouragement for acceptance among culturally different students (Petrović et al., 2016).

In line with this, the previous literature reveals that professors, who are enthusiastic and determined in the achievement of their working tasks, accomplish superior instruction efforts and provide higher quality education in multicultural environments (Kunter, 2013; Kunter et al., 2011; Petrović et al., 2016). Hence the requirement for professors' intercultural skills, awareness, responsiveness and interaction, as the vital elements for their engagement with higher education students, directing, in the long run, the development of an integrating and inclusive society (Dimitrov & Haque, 2016).

2.3. Hypotheses development

The actual quality of education in a culturally diverse environment can be found compromised if professors do not possess knowledge, experience or sensitivity regarding the social distance between the different groups (Leutwyler et al., 2018). Accordingly, intercultural competence is vital for professors' capability to commit to culturally diverse students and environments (Ricardo-Barreto et al., 2022). Professors' intercultural aptitudes are part of a transformative process of building awareness and knowledge about diversity and commitment to social justice in society (Barreto et al., 2017).

Moreover, professional identity and interaction factors, characterizing the employees' dedication, values and beliefs about their job, are highlighted as essential for evaluating professors' performance in higher education (Barbara-i-Molinero et al., 2017; Culver et al., 2021). Professors with mature professional

identities believe in their role in the university. They show commitment to their profession, build balanced relationships in the classroom and promote collaborative working adapted to students' needs (Abu-Alruz & Khasawneh, 2013; Hanna et al., 2020). Concerned with their students' progress, these professors reveal their educational capacity, skills, and the service offered to students as the precursor of eagerness, fulfilment and aptitude to continuously evolve in the higher education environment (Dalal & Akdere, 2021; Efu, 2020; Hanna et al., 2019; Noaman et al., 2017).

Therefore, professors who act in accordance with their professional skills and values, and dedicate themselves to the creation of a balanced learning environment and trusting relationships, contribute to their encouraging attitude, highlighting the purpose of intercultural communication among higher education students (Abacioglu et al., 2020). Professors characterized by a solid professional identity are capable of coping promptly with social educational development and efficiently managing sensible educational environments (Hong et al., 2017). Professors who identify with the need to contribute to building a harmonious relationship with their students, will deliver improved guidance in students' socialization process and carry out their tasks with greater enthusiasm and emotional and social involvement (Hanna et al., 2020). Therefore, it can be expected that professors who have the predisposition towards creating a fruitful and supporting learning environment with their students will show enthusiasm, capacities and commitment to further contribute to a culturally diverse environment.

Consequently, the proposition of the following relationships is suggested:

H1: Professors' identity with their profession will positively impact their cultural diversity enthusiasm.

H2: Professors' identity with their profession will positively impact their cultural diversity self-efficacy.

H3: Professors' identity with their profession will positively impact their commitment to social justice.

Professors presenting an enthusiastic posture of endorsement, and following an attitude that encourages interaction, instruction and social justice among culturally diverse students, is consistent with their personal mission to sustain professors' actions in engaging behaviors (Samuels et al., 2019). Specifically, professors who are willing and prepared to involve actively in the interactivity of the culturally diverse classroom, perceive their working environment as rewarding (Petrović et al., 2016). This enthusiastic approach equips them with the readiness to actively engage with their job tasks (Darling-Hammond et al., 2020). Furthermore, professors who perceive themselves as successful in encouraging students' learning achievements and skillful in providing suitable interaction among culturally different students are more prone to continued cooperation with the community and the institution (Dimitrov & Haque, 2016). Finally, emphasizing the vital role of social justice in a multicultural educational environment, professors who recognize and aim to resolve possible discriminatory attitudes or practices, puts themselves in the position of mediators for social change (Dowd, 2018). Their commitment to social justice as an additional

intercultural competence involves stronger engagement with their working responsibilities (Ozias & Pasque, 2019).

It has been suggested that professors' confidence, self-efficacy and responsibility with teaching in a culturally diverse environment stimulate their fulfilment and encourages continuous engagement in those practices (Carley Rizzuto, 2017; Doran, 2017). Professors equipped with self-efficacy who carry out their operational tasks devotedly and responsibly are known to be prone to engaging more strongly with and investing efforts in their job (Tualalelei & Halse, 2022).

Accordingly, the following hypotheses are proposed:

H4: Professors' cultural diversity enthusiasm will positively impact their engagement.

H5: Professors' cultural diversity self-efficacy will positively impact their engagement.

H6: Professors' commitment to social justice will positively impact their engagement.

The proposed relationships can be observed in the following Figure 1.

Figure 1. Proposed research model

3. Methodology

3.1. Procedure

A review of the literature helped detect substantial elements that describe higher education professors' dedication to multicultural environments, designating professional identification and cultural diversity dimensions as the aspects that institutions need to pursue to accomplish distinction and superiority in the

interaction with students from different cultural backgrounds. Additionally, professors' engagement has been recognized as a key depiction of universities' success among competitors. The final decision on the variables composing the questionnaire was made after a pre-test with 10 researchers, 10 academic personnel representatives and 20 university students, who likewise assisted in the scales' refinement to achieve clarity and precision. Given that the original language of the survey was Macedonian, 3 bilingual speakers, professors of Macedonian and English, assisted in the translation and back-translation of the statements, to guarantee transparency and avoid possible misconceptions (Brislin, 1986).

The scales employed in this research have their base in the previous literature and were adapted to the context of the research. Namely, we used validated scales for measuring professors' identity (Abu-Alruz & Khasawneh, 2013), cultural diversity enthusiasm, self-efficacy and commitment to social justice (Petrović et al., 2016), and engagement (Aboramadan et al., 2019; Schaufeli et al., 2002). 5-point Likert scale measurements (1 – strongly disagree to 5 – strongly agree) were applied to classify respondents' agreement with the statements.

To estimate scales' reliability and validity and confirm the measurement model's robustness, the standard procedure of partial least squares–structural equation modelling was followed (Hair et al., 2020). The relevance and significance of the proposed relationships and the explanatory and predictive power of the structural model were likewise assessed. We used the SmartPLS4 software (Ringle et al., 2015) for the data analyses.

3.2. Sample

The purposive sampling technique, a non-probabilistic method recommended for research of a predefined group of individuals, was employed for exploring higher education professors (Tashakkori & Teddlie, 2010). The final sample of 322 respondents presents a $\pm 5.46\%$ error at a 95% confidence level for the case of maximum uncertainty. The sample size appropriateness was confirmed by power analysis with G*Power software, presenting a power of 99.99%, at $\alpha=0.05$ standard level of significance, $f^2=0.15$ effect size and 3 predictors, exceeding the recommended 80% power level (Cohen, 1988; Faul et al., 2007). The socio-demographic description of the sample reveals it is composed mainly of women (56.2%), representing a typical age between 35 and 54 years (66.4%). The respondents are professors from three public universities in Macedonia, principally the Ss. Cyril and Methodius University (68.6%) and, generally, work at the associate professor and full professor positions (80.1%).

4. Results

4.1. Measurement model estimation

During the scales' refinement in the estimation of the measurement model, a total of 5 items were deleted due to low or non-significant loadings, from the professional identity, cultural diversity enthusiasm, self-efficacy and commitment to social justice constructs (Table 1). The reliability of all the remaining indicators was proved by confirming their adequate loadings (>0.7), significant at a confidence level of $p < 0.01$ (Hair et al., 2017). The reliability and internal consistency of the scales and the convergent validity were validated through satisfactory values for Cronbach's alpha ($\alpha > 0.7$), composite reliability (CR > 0.7) and average variance extracted (AVE > 0.5) (Bagozzi & Yi, 2012).

[Table 1 near here]

The constructs' discriminant validity was corroborated with the Fornell and Larcker criterion (Fornell & Larcker, 1981), where AVE values were verified to be greater than their squared correlations with other constructs. Additionally, the heterotrait-monotrait ratio (HTMT) (Henseler et al., 2015) revealed the same outcome by affirming consistency with the predetermined limit of 0.9 (Table 2).

[Table 2 near here]

The model's good fit was evidenced through the standardised root mean square residual (SRMR) value of 0.048, respecting the threshold of 0.08 (Hair et al., 2019; Hu & Bentler, 1998).

4.2. Hypotheses testing

Once the measurement model was validated, it was proceeded with the structural model estimation. Accordingly, R^2 values exceeding the recommended 0.1 (0.148 for cultural diversity enthusiasm, 0.177 for cultural diversity self-efficacy, 0.185 for commitment to social justice and 0.117 for engagement) confirmed the model's explanatory power (Hair et al., 2019). Furthermore, the proposed hypotheses were tested, to conclude that 5 out of 6 relationships were supported (Table 3). In addition, the model's predictive relevance was validated through Q^2 values of 0.114 for cultural diversity enthusiasm, 0.147 for cultural diversity self-efficacy, 0.136 for commitment to social justice and 0.079 for engagement, respectively.

[Table 3 near here]

In addition, the potential alterations in the model's interactions were assessed through the control analysis, by which the explanatory power of the model was controlled and the investigation of higher education professors with similar perceptions guaranteed (Kock, 2015; Román-Calderón et al., 2016). It was confirmed that gender ($\beta=0.155$, $t=2.939$), age ($\beta= -0.080$, $t=1.536$), university ($\beta= -0.038$, $t=0.643$), job position ($\beta= 0.012$, $t=0.187$) and field of study ($\beta=0.133$, $t=2.849$) did not amend in any way the proposed relationships for higher education professors' interaction in a multicultural environment.

Finally, following literature recommendations (Zhao et al., 2010), the indirect effects were observed to measure the mediating effects of the cultural diversity enthusiasm, self-efficacy and social justice dimensions. The only significant relationship was confirmed in the case of commitment to social justice (professors' identity \rightarrow commitment to social justice \rightarrow professors' engagement) with $\beta=0.081$, $t=1.965$, endorsing the importance of professors' commitment to creating engagement with their work.

5. Discussion and conclusion

Intercultural competence can be observed in the individual commitment to act with respect and avoid issues that could jeopardize communication in a culturally diverse environment, pointing out its importance for personal and professional relationships. In the research of intercultural education at higher education institutions, intercultural competence is recognized as the tool for appropriate interaction and social inclusion in multicultural or multi-ethnic societies (Pareja de Vicente et al., 2021). In this sense, while it has been widely recognized that professors need concrete training for adequate responsiveness to different learners (Auer & Tsiatsos, 2018; Müller et al., 2020; Starčević et al., 2022), the precise motivation for or impact of those attitudes have not been observed. Drawing on the Western Balkan situation, represented by multicultural societies, it becomes vital to study the extent to which intercultural skills and capabilities can be seen as valuable for the higher education environment as the reflection point for building receptive citizens. Therefore, the study objective explores how professors' identity with interaction with students determines their cultural diversity competences and furthermore their predisposition towards engagement with their job. The proposed model has explicitly confirmed the professors' predisposition to work in culturally diverse higher education environment and has contributed with a distinctive investigation of personal resources in the given circumstances of multicultural classrooms. It can be concluded that to achieve a firmer professors' engagement with the higher education system, the professor-student interaction should be closely observed, as the element that could intensify or worsen participation and carve the multicultural learning atmosphere. This investigation underpinned the role of intercultural competency, whose significance rises in conditions of challenging job settings.

The findings confirm the distinctiveness of professors' involvement in creating a pleasant learning atmosphere and adapting to students' needs as the trigger for additional development of intercultural competence. Namely, professors' efforts to support and follow students' progress increases their enthusiasm to work in a multicultural setting (H1), their perception of self-efficacy in the performance of tasks in a culturally diverse classroom (H2) and their commitment to social justice to avoid conflict caused by cultural differences (H3). Professors' greater care for offering valuable content and context to multicultural classrooms acts as a motivator for their intercultural implication. This conclusion indicates similarity with previous research suggesting in general terms that professors who identify with their role as educators and possess capacities to create balanced relationships with students, might demonstrate more outstanding teaching practices and encouraging attitude toward the communication of diversity (Abacioglu et al., 2020; Garwe, 2015; Tualaulelei & Halse, 2022).

Furthermore, the research results reveal that professor-student intercultural interaction shapes professors' engagement with their work. Specifically, professors who perceive themselves competent to build satisfactory relationships with students and respond to individual needs, are prone to show further job engagement (H5). Similarly, their dedication to protecting students from discrimination plays a crucial role in their engagement in the working place (H6). According to earlier assumptions, professors' intercultural competence could determine their commitment to culturally diverse classrooms (Dimitrov & Haque, 2016; Ricardo-Barreto et al., 2022). However, it is noteworthy mentioning that professors' interest and eagerness to work in a multicultural classroom do not impact their engagement (H4). The reason for this might lie in the fact that, even though professors' might show enthusiasm to work in a culturally diverse environment, if they do not possess actual competence to support and protect students' learning and communication, it will be difficult for them to really engage with the work in a multicultural classroom (Darling-Hammond et al., 2020).

Also, as validated that the proposed relationships were not altered in any way by the control variables, the findings can guarantee homogeneous implications regarding higher education professors' interaction and engagement with culturally diverse classrooms.

To summarize, professors' sensibility for social justice might be the decisive element distinguishing educators prepared for devoted interaction in multicultural higher education environments. To be precise, professors' beliefs characterizing their social interaction with and dedication to students can be critical for evaluating higher education performance (Barbara-i-Molinero et al., 2017; Culver et al., 2021).

In this sense, the current study provides unique empirical evidence of the impact of professors' identity with students' needs, as an indispensable instigator for developing cultural diversity competencies and social justice attitudes, for the fortification of engaging responses towards the higher education multicultural environment. The distinctiveness of the research can be observed in the explanation of the

intercultural competence as a source and outcome of professors' interaction with students from different cultural, religious or linguistic backgrounds, adding value to the social development and sustainability of contemporary relationships in Western Balkan societies.

5.1. Academic and managerial implications

This research provides several significant implications to the literature on higher education service consumption. First, higher education systems have been evaluated to a greater extent in light of students' perceptions of the institutional quality, support or value (Binnawas et al., 2020; Haverila et al., 2020), neglecting the fact that a university's authority is vastly determined by its employees' effort, which identifies educational quality and resources as the indicators for universities to define their distinction (Prakash, 2018). Indeed, university professors' capabilities represent the assets that, in the long run, will provide value to the institution through socially involved professionals, engaged in delivering quality education. Bearing in mind that engagement is a product of motivations related to the professors' academic contribution (Dalal & Akdere, 2021; Klahn Acuña & Male, 2022), it becomes crucial to point out the implication of understanding their commitment building as a result of their own competencies and practices. Second, the professional identity has been observed in the previous literature in a more general sense, through a variety of constructs, yet usually defining its reflection as a measure of employees' commitment (Hanna et al., 2019), instead of contemplating it as a predecessor. Additionally, in this study, professors' identity is explicitly related to students' needs for progress in a multicultural environment. Hence the value of contemplating higher educational institutions through professors' self-reflection, as a tool to identify and pursue meaningful continuing professional development.

Third, it is relatively unknown how universities manage the intercultural knowledge, skills and capabilities that policymakers consider valuable to students' future (Tualaulelei & Halse, 2022). Therefore, positioning the engagement and the professional identity in the context of a multicultural classroom, explaining the antecedents and impacts of higher education professors' interaction with culturally diverse students, provides this research with a unique distinction. As well, focusing the study on a Western Balkan country adds to the body of knowledge of higher education systems in developing countries, recognizing forms for improving higher education on its path towards tolerant and respectful educational opportunities.

With all this in mind, this work makes a notable contribution by enhancing the limited understanding of scholars and executives on the role of professors' competency and effort in a multicultural higher education system. Finally, offering a clearer picture of the communication in a culturally diverse environment, the insights identify potential obstacles in the working process and protect higher education institutions' relationships.

The practical implications of the study's findings are important to be considered from a managerial perspective. Thus, first, we have to consider that companies' general tendency currently is short-term oriented, due to political and economic alterations, the increased digitalization of services, and the social conditions, challenging societies worldwide. Nevertheless, actually, it is the right moment to be future and long-term-oriented, preserving resources to maintain quality service for the public (Sull et al., 2020). Therefore, it is essential to provide professors with suitable working conditions, so they continuously perform with engagement and, in this way, offer superior educational service and preserve the established relationships.

Universities should tailor their environment to professors' needs, while providing support and training for enhancing professors' aptitudes. The greater the professors' predisposition and capacities for adequate interaction with students, the higher the probability for engaged professionals in the delivery of valuable higher education. Professors' favorable attitudes and opinions are indispensable for their responsiveness to culturally diverse students, but higher education institutions play an essential role in stirring and reinforcing these perspectives (Tualaulelei & Halse, 2022). Therefore, universities should focus on encouraging professors' motivation to build and cultivate relationships with students, aiming to offer them a productive and pleasant learning environment. By raising awareness about professors' social values, a contribution will be made to professor-student interaction and relationship development. Then, through public interventions to promote professors' role in the community or sharing students' expectations and impact stories, higher education institutions can offer a glimpse into professors' recognition.

Employees' own critical evaluation of their relationships and performance in the working environment has been considered a powerful instrument for recognizing their professional development (Efu, 2020), accentuating the recommendation for universities to seriously contemplate professors' interaction and dedication to students and enable its course as the means for developing progress and engagement with the institution and the higher education system. Professors' skills and willingness for involvement in multicultural environments evidence their self-efficacy, self-reflection and self-confidence (Tualaulelei & Halse, 2021). Thus, to involve professors, universities must reassure their position and integrity in the institution, and promote harmonious collaboration, while being especially careful to stimulate their capacities and excellence development, especially through the challenging diversity of a multicultural classroom.

The valuable working and learning settings, enabling equal and respectful educational opportunities for students with different cultural backgrounds, create the foundation for professors to feel inspired, enthusiastic and proud of their job, as the elements designating engaged employees. Higher education institutions are responsible for extending professional opportunities for educators to acquire knowledge, which could later reflect through committed exercise and practical engagement in continuous professional

development (Meijer et al., 2016). Therefore, universities should endorse professors' ability to recognize individual learning and communication requirements and adapt the conditions for students from different cultures.

The acknowledgement of professors' intercultural capacities, understood as a socially inclusive process of interaction in culturally distinct societies, underpins the significance of understanding students' social, cultural or personal characteristics as the criterion for tolerant collaboration (Pareja de Vicente et al., 2021). Therefore, professors' continuous commitment to social values, inclusion and conflict mitigation, through different workshops or seminars for the whole academic community, will result in an enriching educational environment where culturally diverse individuals can reflect their own values and evolve without prejudices and discrimination.

The present implications serve as a valuable indicator of how the higher education system is perceived in a developing society, underlining the necessity to seriously consider, in educational policy and practice, the issue of cultural, religious or linguistic diversity. Intercultural competencies are a necessary condition for individuals acting in globalized international societies aiming to shrink the social distance among culturally different groups.

5.2. Limitations and future research

This research identifies a few limitations that could be overcome in future research. First, the restriction in the generalization of the results to a broader area, due to the investigation of the case of Macedonian higher education professors, would be mitigated by replicating the survey in several Western Balkan countries, enabling in this way a comparison among higher education systems. Second, bearing in mind the earlier transition and the changing political events occurring in the country, it might be valuable to perform a longitudinal study that would follow the evolution of higher education with respect to the development of intercultural communication and interaction, as representative of the Macedonian society. Third, an assessment of similarities and differences could be contemplated for public vs private universities, as a contrast of institutions with potentially different involvement in social issues. Finally, in order to offer a more accurate image of the higher education system, it would be helpful if the opinions of the students and the institutions were likewise included in the survey, in a manner that each party's effort, support and implication will be evaluated by students, professors and university management.

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Table 1. Measurement model

Construct name and measurement items	λ
<i>Professors' identity (AVE=.707; α=.916; CR=.935)</i>	
I create and maintain a flexible and harmonious learning environment for my students.	.887
I help students apply what they have learned to their daily work life.	.853
I establish a trusting and caring relationship with my students.	.866
My students regard me as a role model because of my positive social values.	.733
I find satisfaction in supporting lifelong learning of students.	.849
I tailor my teaching to fit the needs, interests, and abilities of my students.	.847
I discuss the progress of my students with colleagues.	deleted
<i>Cultural diversity enthusiasm (AVE=.775; α=.903; CR=.932)</i>	
I like teaching students from different cultural backgrounds.	.892
For me, teaching in multicultural classes is a challenge, not an obstacle.	deleted
It is a pleasure to work in a culturally diverse classroom, although it is not always easy.	.905
I enjoy the teachers' privilege of dealing with many culturally diverse students.	.906
I am looking forward to taking over a class with great cultural variety.	.815
<i>Cultural diversity self-efficacy (AVE=.841; α=.953; CR=.963)</i>	
I am sure that I can make good contact with minority students.	deleted
Even if I teach a class with a large cultural diversity, I am able to respond to different individual needs.	.906
I think that I am able to recognize the learning requirements of the individual students, even in classes with a large cultural diversity.	.908
I am ready to work in a multicultural environment.	.880
I know I can do a lot to support the learning process of minority students.	.950
I am competent in creating learning conditions in which minority students will feel successful.	.940
<i>Commitment to social justice (AVE=.755; α=.918; CR=.939)</i>	
I do not allow jokes in the classroom that undermine students of other cultures.	deleted
I encourage students to help each other in order to achieve equal chances.	deleted
I always try to resolve a conflict between my students caused by cultural differences.	.825
I always make sure that the assignments I give to students do not discriminate against minority students.	.819
I react immediately if students show prejudice towards other cultures.	.867
I immediately react when I have the impression that a minority student is excluded from social activities.	.915
I immediately react when I have the impression that a minority student is rejected.	.912
<i>Professors' engagement (AVE=.708; α=.895; CR=.923)</i>	
To me, my job is challenging.	.734
My job inspires me.	.917
I am enthusiastic about my job.	.896
I am proud of the work that I do.	.863
I find the work that I do full of meaning and purpose.	.783

Note: All loadings are significant at a confidence level $p < .01$

Table 2. Latent variables correlation matrix vs heterotrait-monotrait ratio (HTMT)

	PI	CDE	CDSE	CSJ	PE
Professors' identity (PI)		<i>.419</i>	<i>.444</i>	<i>.466</i>	<i>.461</i>
Cultural diversity enthusiasm (CDE)	.385		<i>.836</i>	<i>.705</i>	<i>.298</i>
Cultural diversity self-efficacy (CDSE)	.421	.802		<i>.753</i>	<i>.333</i>
Commitment to social justice (CSJ)	.430	.640	.704		<i>.342</i>
Professors' engagement (PE)	.416	.274	.313	.317	

Note: Lower diagonal shows the correlation matrix and upper diagonal (*italic*) presents HTMT values

Table 3. Structural model estimation

Hypothesized relationships	Coefficient β	t Value	Result
H1: Professors' identity with their profession will positively impact their cultural diversity enthusiasm.	.385	5.536***	Supported
H2: Professors' identity with their profession will positively impact their cultural diversity self-efficacy.	.421	5.864***	Supported
H3: Professors' identity with their profession will positively impact their commitment to social justice.	.430	5.783***	Supported
H4: Professors' cultural diversity enthusiasm will positively impact their engagement.	.024	0.247 ^{ns}	Not supported
H5: Professors' cultural diversity self-efficacy will positively impact their engagement.	.161	1.681*	Supported
H6: Professors' commitment to social justice will positively impact their engagement.	.188	2.328**	Supported

Note: ns - not significant; * $p < .1$; ** $p < .05$; *** $p < .01$